

Political and Operational Stability in the Global Innovation Index

Angelo Leogrande, Lum University Giuseppe Degennaro, leogrande.culture@lum.it

The variable "Political and operational stability" within the Global Innovation Index (GII) refers to the stability of a country or region from both the political governance and operational context perspectives. This stability is crucial for fostering innovation, as a secure and reliable political and operational environment encourages investments and the growth of economic activities. Political stability measures the degree of security within a country, assessing the presence of conflicts, insurgencies, or governmental instability that could compromise economic activities. A politically stable context thus provides a favorable environment for innovation development, as it reduces risks associated with drastic changes or internal unrest. On the other hand, operational stability concerns the reliability of a country's institutions and economic and legal infrastructures. A transparent, predictable, and well-functioning legal and regulatory system enables businesses to operate efficiently, ensuring continuity and reducing risks for investments in research, development, and innovation. In summary, within the GII framework, political and operational stability is essential to creating an environment conducive to innovation, as it mitigates risks and encourages engagement in innovative activities. The data refer to the period between 2013 and 2022.

Political and Operational Stability in 2022. The data on political and operational stability of countries for 2022 provides an insightful overview of the capacity of nations to maintain a favorable environment for economic, technological, and innovative development. Political and operational stability is a crucial factor in promoting investor confidence, sustainable economic growth, and the ability to attract talent. Countries that demonstrate a high degree of stability are generally more capable of providing a secure and predictable environment for economic activities and innovation. At the top of the rankings is Singapore, which achieved the highest score of 100, confirming its status as a model of political and operational stability. This result aligns with Singapore's reputation as one of the most efficient and well-governed countries in the world, with a strong rule of law and stable economic policies that make it a global hub for innovation and business. New Zealand, with a score of 96.4, and Brunei Darussalam, with 94.5, follow in the rankings, reflecting their ability to maintain a stable political context and reliable operational framework. In Europe, countries like Denmark, Iceland, and Luxembourg, with scores of 90.9, reaffirm their traditional political stability and a favorable environment for economic development. These countries, known for their well-established democracies and strong social systems, offer an operational framework that fosters innovation, with robust infrastructures and reliable legal systems. Nations like Japan and Switzerland, with scores of 89.1 and 85.5 respectively, maintain their positions as global leaders in stability, which reflects their ability to successfully manage both economic and political challenges. In the mid-range, we find countries like the United States (78.2) and the United Kingdom (74.5), which, although still relatively stable, are facing significant challenges. For the United States, internal political tensions and growing polarization may have contributed to a slight decline in the perception of its political stability. The United Kingdom, on the other hand, has faced turbulence resulting from Brexit and the economic uncertainties that followed, negatively affecting its score. Among emerging countries, Vietnam (76.4) and Rwanda (76.4) stand out as notable examples of improvement in political and operational stability. These countries have undertaken significant reforms that have strengthened their governance and improved their economic prospects, making them more attractive to foreign

investment. On the opposite end of the spectrum, countries like Iraq (25.4), Nigeria (45.5), and Zimbabwe (45.5) rank among the lowest, reflecting years of political instability, internal conflicts, and governance issues that have severely compromised their operational environment. These challenging contexts make it extremely difficult to attract investment and develop innovative sectors, hindering economic growth. In conclusion, the data shows a clear correlation between political and operational stability and a country's ability to thrive economically. Nations with high scores enjoy strong investor confidence and a favorable environment for innovation. Conversely, countries with low scores face significant challenges that limit their potential for sustainable development.

Political and Operational Stability Between 2013 and 2022. The analysis of political and operational stability data from 2013 to 2022 shows a notable variety of improvements and regressions in the countries considered, with some emerging trends reflecting the complexity of global politics and economic dynamics. One of the most significant aspects is the clear improvement in countries that have historically faced difficulties in terms of political stability. Nigeria, for instance, recorded a significant increase of 26.9 points, with a percentage change of 144.62%. This can be attributed to a series of institutional reforms and the consolidation of democracy in the country, although issues related to security and corruption persist. Other African nations, such as Côte d'Ivoire and Rwanda, have shown similar improvements, with Côte d'Ivoire gaining 35.8 points (113.65%) and Rwanda 11.4 points (17.54%). This demonstrates how political reforms and post-conflict stabilization have had positive effects, contributing to the creation of a more favorable environment for economic growth and innovation. On the other hand, some Southeast Asian countries, such as the Philippines and Bangladesh, have shown considerable improvements in political and operational stability, with percentage changes exceeding 90%. These results indicate that, despite internal challenges like poverty and governance issues, progress has been made in strengthening institutions. China, with an improvement of 21.9 points (44.69%), reflects the country's ability to maintain operational stability despite geopolitical turmoil and increasing tensions with the West. Israel also saw a change of 106.71%, which may be linked to its strong capacity to manage security and the stability of its institutions despite regional difficulties. In contrast, countries that have historically boasted strong stability are showing signs of regression. A striking example is Finland, which saw a decline of 14.5 points, signaling that even Nordic countries, often considered models of stability, are facing new challenges. Austria and Switzerland, with drops of -11.7 and -12.3 points, respectively, reveal a downturn related to internal issues, possibly tied to global economic uncertainties or growing political polarization. Southern European countries, such as Italy (-11.4 points) and Spain (-5.1 points), also registered declines, suggesting that the economic and political crises of recent years have left deep scars. Another clear trend is the decline in Middle Eastern countries. Qatar (-19.4 points) and Saudi Arabia (-6.1 points) show signs of instability, partly due to geopolitical tensions and economic challenges linked to the collapse of oil prices. The decrease in stability in Ukraine (-11.6 points) is particularly alarming, reflecting the devastating impact of the war that began in 2022. Overall, the data highlights how the concept of political and operational stability is heavily influenced not only by internal factors but also by global and regional dynamics. The improvement in many developing countries indicates a process of institutional consolidation, while the decline in some developed countries and the Middle East demonstrates that stability cannot be taken for granted, and new challenges, such as economic crises and geopolitical conflicts, can quickly erode even the most solid foundations.

Conclusions. On average, the value of political and operational stability between 2013 and 2022 increased by 5.92%, rising from 65.94 units to 69.85 units. The top performers are Nigeria with +144.62%, Côte d'Ivoire with +113.65%, Nepal with +107.12%, Israel with +106.71%, and

Bangladesh with +97.96%. However, some countries experienced a significant decline in political and operational stability, including the United Arab Emirates with -18.86%, Namibia with -19.34%, Qatar with -20.25%, Zambia with -25.10%, and Mozambique with -25.14%.

Source: Global Innovation Index

Link: <https://www.wipo.int/web/global-innovation-index>

Performance	Countries	2013	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
Top Performers	Nigeria	18,6	45,5	26,9	144,62
	Cote d'Ivoire	31,5	67,3	35,8	113,65
	Nepal	28,1	58,2	30,1	107,12
	Israel	34,3	70,9	36,6	106,71
	Bangladesh	29,4	58,2	28,8	97,96
Worse Performers	United Arab Emirates	89,6	72,7	-16,9	-18,86
	Namibia	87,9	70,9	-17	-19,34
	Qatar	95,8	76,4	-19,4	-20,25
	Zambia	77,7	58,2	-19,5	-25,1
	Mozambique	72,8	54,5	-18,3	-25,14

References

Leogrande, A., Saponaro, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). A GIS based estimation of quality of life in Italian regions. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR) e-ISSN*.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Research and Development Expenditures on ESG Model in the Global Economy. Available at SSRN 4414232.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., Angelo, L., & Matarrese, M. M. (2023). The intellectual assets in Europe. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 27(2), 1-13.

Magazzino, C., & Leogrande, A. (2021). Subjective well-being in Italian regions: A panel data approach. *Applied econometrics and international development*, 21(1), 1-18.

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The attractiveness of European research systems. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(10), 72-101.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Role of Political Stability in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. Available at SSRN 4406997.

Leogrande, A. (2023). The Rule of Law in the ESG Framework in the World Economy. Available at SSRN 4355016.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Role of Government Effectiveness in the Light of ESG Data at Global Level. Available at SSRN 4324938.

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The impact of R&D investments on corporate performance in European Countries. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(7), 186-201.

Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Labor Force Participation Rate in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. Available at SSRN 4466452.

Angelo, L., Laureti, L., & Alberto, C. (2022). The Innovation Index in Europe. Available at SSRN 4091597.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Enterprises Providing ICT Training in Europe. Available at SSRN 4021150.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., Leogrande, A., & Matarrese, M. (2021). The Innovation Linkages in Europe. Available at SSRN 3983218.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Ease of Doing Business in the ESG Framework at World Level. Available at SSRN 4420946.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Voice and Accountability in the ESG Framework in a Global Perspective. Available at SSRN 4398483.

Leogrande, A. (2022). Mortality from Cancer in the Italian Regions. *International Web Post*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Satisfaction with the Environmental Condition in the Italian Regions between 2004 and 2020. Available at SSRN 4061708.

